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STK17a and STK17b are HER2+ kinase addiction targets.

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Citations

1. Short, S.P., Thompson, J.J., Bilotta, A.J., Chen, X., Revetta, F.L., Washington, M.K. and Williams, C.S., 2019. Serine threonine kinase 17A maintains the epithelial state in colorectal cancer cells. *Molecular cancer research*, 17(4), pp.882-894.
2. Yan, Z., Han, Z., Wang, Y., Beus, M., Zhang, Y., Picado, A., Wells, C.I., Wu, J., Weidenhammer, L.B., Pires, K.M. and Leibold, E.A., 2026. Targeting STK17B kinase activates ferroptosis and suppresses drug resistance in multiple myeloma. *Blood*, 147(1), pp.48-60.